

Car Recommendation Using Machine Learning

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Abstract-- As the amounts of cars booking are exponentially increasing because of that finding relevant cars are important to those who purchase cars, for this a Personal recommendation systems have been emerged to conduct effective search which mine most booked cars based on user rating and interest. This paper proposed an effective system for recommending cars for online users that rated a car using the content based filtering or collaborative filtering and then found out the best cars and suggest them. For this system, two datasets have been used one about the different cars and the other one about the rating for the cars by different users. In this work KNN algorithm is used to find best cars according to the user taste. To implement this system Pycharm is used as a developing software. Many python libraries like pandas, numpy, scipy, sklearn etc. is used.

Keywords: Nearest-Neighbors, KNN, csr_matrix

I. INTRODUCTION

By implementing recommendation engine on the websites, e-commerce and retail companies are using the potential of data and increasing sales. It's a great opportunity to learn more about this incredible machine learning approach as the application cases for these systems have been gradually growing over the past few years. In order to recommend products that are most likely to be of interest to users, recommender systems attempt to forecast their preferences. The information needed for recommender systems comes from explicit user reviews after seeing a film or listening to a music, through implicit search history and past purchases, or from other information about the users or the objects themselves. Sites like Spotify, YouTube, or Netflix utilize such information to promote playlists, so-called Daily mixes, or to suggest videos, respectively. There are different types of recommendation systems like content-based systems and collaborative filtering systems. This system is using collaborative filtering system etc. Currently, one of the most popular methods is collaborative filtering, which typically yields superior results than content-based recommendations. Collaborative filtering is an unsupervised. There are many algorithms in unsupervised machine learning, for the proposed system, using one of them to build the System that is using KNN and other python libraries for the development. K-Nearest-Neighbor is a straightforward algorithm that sorts new information or instances based on similarities between them and all previously stored examples. A data point is often categorized using the classification of its neighbor's. The number of nearest neighbors to include in the majority of the rating is indicated by the parameter "k" in the KNN algorithm. By using this machine learning technique, this system will recommend product most user would likely to buy. This is method is developed because of pervious users rating. This

system is going through many python libraries, methods, algorithm for the development of the system. For this system dataset is a self-developed from a large dataset. System finding the best output from a large dataset where about ten thousand amount of data are stored.

II. RELATED WORKS

There are many machine learning techniques used to recommend different products, videos or music etc..., Machine learning algorithms like K-means clustering, KNN (k-nearest neighbors), Singular value decomposition etc... are used. All these are unsupervised learning algorithms. Unsupervised learning is done either by clustering method or association method.

Sarma et. al. [1] described about different machine learning techniques. Using K-means Cosine Distance function to measure distance and Cosine Similarity by this method the result was found, Implementation and the system is for the recommendation of books for the different users. The fault of the system is that needed a large number of user's data for recommending books.

Roya et. al. [2] by using different algorithms system find accuracy of recommendation. Used Random Forest, Multinomial Naive Bayes, Logistic Regression. the result of finding was the accuracy. However, system failed to find which is the best recommendation algorithm.

Goyani et. al. [3] described about different recommendation system that are using these days. However, failed to build a recommendation system according to the study.

Furtado et. al. [4] By using k-Nearest-Neighbors algorithm for the system and recommend movies to user. System is using the past ratings of the user about the movies.

Li et. al. [5] Used different data mining techniques for the development of recommendation system. Data mining is an emerging field in analysis of different data. Which is used to improve the recommendation quality.

III. METHOD OF RECOMMENDATION

Two different dataset plays the important role in the system one is about the car (cars.csv) dataset which contains carid and car model and the other one is ratings (ratings.csv) of the cars done by other users. This two dataset are self-developed from a large dataset. Since the large dataset didn't meet the requirements for the system development, dataset is built for the system. Large

dataset is collected from kaggle. Then afterwards this dataset is broken down and combined specifically for the system

The process consists of two phases:

1. Training phase:

The dataset's data are used to train the system, which then fits a model using the selected algorithm. Then convert the dataset into a matrix format for testing phase

2. Testing phase:

The system receives inputs and is tested to make sure it functions properly. Since the accuracy is confirmed, the data testing purposes must be appropriate. Compare user rating dataset and different cars ready to give a most accurate output after the user enter the which car he need and after processing user input and dataset data the system will recommend a best output for the user.

The following are the key features that are affecting in the recommendation:

- Ratings
- Make
- Carid
- Userid

Figure 1: Sample data(cars.csv)

	A	B	C	D
1	carId	make		
2		1 Sienna SE		
3		2 F-150 Lariat		
4		3 1500 Laramie		
5		4 Accord Sport SE		
6		5 RX 350		
7		6 4Runner SR5		
8		7 HR-V LX		
9		8 E-Class E 350		
10		9 Pilot Touring 8-Passenger		
11		10 Charger Scat Pack		
12		11 RC 350 Base		
13		12 GS 350 Base		
14		13 RX 350 Base		

Figure 2: Sample data(ratings.csv)

	A	B	C	D
1	userId	carId	rating	
2		1	1	4.6
3		2	2	4.8
4		3	3	4.7
5		4	4	5
6		5	5	4.8
7		6	6	4.7
8		7	7	4.6
9		8	8	4.8
10		9	9	4.8
11		10	10	4.8
12		11	11	4.8

A. Techniques Used

- k-nearest neighbors

The supervised learning technique K-nearest-neighbor's (KNN) is used for both regression and classification. By calculating the distance between the test data and all of the training points, KNN tries to predict the proper class for the test data. Then choose the K spots that are closest to the test data. The KNN method determines which classes of the "K" training data the test data will belong to, and the class with the highest probability is chosen. The value in a regression situation is the average of the 'K' chosen training points.

Figure 3: KNN algorithm

```

from sklearn.neighbors import NearestNeighbors
def find_similar_cars(car_id, X, k, metric='cosine', show_distance=False):
    neighbour_ids = []

    car_ind = car_mapper[car_id]
    car_vec = X[car_ind]
    k += 1
    knn = NearestNeighbors(n_neighbors=k, algorithm="brute", metric=metric)
    knn.fit(X)
    car_vec = car_vec.reshape(1, -1)
    neighbour = knn.kneighbors(car_vec, return_distance=show_distance)
    for i in range(0, k):
        n = neighbour.item(i)
        neighbour_ids.append(car_inv_mapper[n])
    neighbour_ids.pop(0)
    return neighbour_ids
    
```

IV. RESULTS

After entering user input for which user given. And according to the user input the algorithm checks the datasets and find the best recommend output for the user.

Figure and Explanation given below: -

1. Reading the data from dataset and give how many ratings and users are found in the dataset printed.

```
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
import sklearn
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import seaborn as sns

import warnings

warnings.simplefilter(action='ignore', category=FutureWarning)

ratings = pd.read_csv("ratings.csv")
ratings.head()

cars = pd.read_csv("cars.csv")
cars.head()

n_ratings = len(ratings)
n_cars = len(ratings['carId'].unique())
n_users = len(ratings['userId'].unique())

print(f"Number of ratings: {n_ratings}")
print(f"Number of unique carId's: {n_cars}")
print(f"Number of unique users: {n_users}")
print(f"Average ratings per user: {round(n_ratings / n_users, 2)}")
print(f"Average ratings per cars: {round(n_ratings / n_cars, 2)}")
```

Output:

```
E:\PyCharm\seminarimplnt\venv\Scripts
Number of ratings: 18758
Number of unique carId's: 9379
Number of unique users: 100
Average ratings per user: 187.58
Average ratings per cars: 2.0
```

2. Converting the dataset into matrix.

```
from scipy.sparse import csr_matrix

def create_matrix(df):
    N = len(df['userId'].unique())
    M = len(df['carId'].unique())

    # Map Ids to indices
    user_mapper = dict(zip(np.unique(df["userId"]), list(range(N))))
    car_mapper = dict(zip(np.unique(df["carId"]), list(range(M))))

    # Map indices to IDs
    user_inv_mapper = dict(zip(list(range(N)), np.unique(df["userId"])))
    car_inv_mapper = dict(zip(list(range(M)), np.unique(df["carId"])))

    user_index = [user_mapper[i] for i in df['userId']]
    car_index = [car_mapper[i] for i in df['carId']]

    X = csr_matrix((df["rating"], (car_index, user_index)), shape=(M, N))

    return X, user_mapper, car_mapper, user_inv_mapper, car_inv_mapper

X, user_mapper, car_mapper, user_inv_mapper, car_inv_mapper = create_matrix(ratings)
```

3. Created matrix is passed to KNN algorithm for further processing.

```
from sklearn.neighbors import NearestNeighbors

def find_similar_cars(car_id, X, k, metric='cosine', show_distance=False):
    neighbour_ids = []

    car_ind = car_mapper[car_id]
    car_vec = X[car_ind]
    k += 1
    knn = NearestNeighbors(n_neighbors=k, algorithm="brute", metric=metric)
    knn.fit(X)
    car_vec = car_vec.reshape(1, -1)
    neighbour = knn.kneighbors(car_vec, return_distance=show_distance)
    for i in range(0, k):
        n = neighbour.item(i)
        neighbour_ids.append(car_inv_mapper[n])
    neighbour_ids.pop(0)
    return neighbour_ids
```

4. After processing, and then system will buy an input of the car which user likes and then after that system will recommend the best output for the user.

```
car_make = dict(zip(cars['carId'], cars['make']))
car_id = int(input("Enter the car id you have : "))
similar_ids = find_similar_cars(car_id, X, k=10)
car_title = car_make[car_id]
print(f"Since you are looking for car : {car_title}")
print("Recommend Cars are : ")
for i in similar_ids:
    print(car_make[i])
```

Output:

```
Enter the car id you have : 48
Since you are looking for car : Civic EX
Recommend Cars are :
X5 xDrive40i
GLE 350 Base
540 i
Yukon SLT
Forester Limited
Atlas Cross Sport 3.6L V6 SEL
540 i xDrive
CX-5 Touring
Sentra SV
Telluride SX
```

CONCLUSION

These days' peoples are booking many cars through online and this type of use case are increasing now a day. Because of that using recommendation system for recommend best cars for the new customers who would like to buy new cars. For building this system KNN algorithm is used which is a machine learning technique used for recommendation and developed, then found out the result from the dataset which contain the data about other user rating on different cars. Thus this implementation is a successful recommendation.

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